

Report on the Special Session ‘Co-creation for advancing ocean observations of marine life – connecting the Baltic Sea to the global ocean’

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INTRODUCTION

The special session entitled ‘Co-creation for advancing ocean observations of marine life – connecting the Baltic Sea to the global ocean’ took place on Thursday, 29 May 2025. The session comprised an invited plenary contribution as part of the 2025 Baltic Sea Science Congress, which took place on 26–30 May 2025 in Sopot, Poland. The session abstract can be found online along with the programme of the entire Congress [here](#).

The session was organized by BioEcoOcean’s Baltic Sea Living Lab members Lina Mtwana Nordlund (Uppsala University, Sweden) and Florian Lüsrow (Uppsala University, Sweden), together with their counterparts from IO PAN, Artur Palacz and Dominik Krzyimiński. The session aimed at discussing how the Baltic Sea stakeholders can maximize every single ocean observation carried out, improve interoperability of Baltic Sea research, and foster greater collaboration among stakeholders, disciplines, and nations.

The session included a Keynote presentation by Lina Mtwana Nordlund, who introduced the BioEcoOcean project and its aim to develop a novel communications support tool: the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science. Lina reflected on the current state of marine life observations globally and in the Baltic Sea, thus setting the scene for the ensuing discussion by an expert panel.

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Photo 1: Lina Mtwana Nordlund presenting the BioEcoOcean project during BSSC-2025 (photo by Dominik Krzyminski).

The experts on the panel included Lina Mtwana Nordlund, Owen Rowe (HELCOM Secretariat), Josefine Larsson (Marint Centrum, Sweden), Laura Tuomi (FMI, Finland), and Markus Meier (IOW, Germany). The session included an interactive questions and answers component recorded via Mentimeter (menti.com), which gave an opportunity to engage the audience gathered in the conference room (over 250 registered participants). The discussion was moderated by Artur Palacz.

This report summarizes the proceedings and outcomes of this special session, reflecting on the expert and audience perception of the state and future of Baltic Sea observations with a focus on marine life.

APPROACH

The plenary discussion centred around three thematic questions, posed to both the panel of experts and the audience. Questions were displayed on the screens surrounding the conference hall whereby the audience used their electronic devices to access the online survey. While the expert panel responded to the thematic questions, the audience perspectives were also collected using

Mentimeter and projected in real-time on the screens. This allowed the moderator and experts on the panel to directly respond to the audience perspectives.

The format of the three questions posed to the audience included both open-ended and closed-ended questions. Open-ended responses were diverse and later grouped by thematic area. Closed-ended questions used a 1 to 10 scale, and responses were collected and visualised in real time using Mentimeter.

Photo 2: Presentation of panel experts during the special session organized by BioEcoOcean during BSSC-2025. Photo by Dominik Krzywiński).

Figure 1. The geographical distribution of the audience's work location.

Question 1: “Tell us something we are doing well in the Baltic Sea, particularly when it comes to observations of marine life.”

This question aimed to identify the strengths in marine life observations in the Baltic Sea. A total of 95 responses were recorded in Mentimeter. The wide range of answers highlighted the diversity of perspectives, which necessitated the grouping of answers to enable meaningful analysis. Grouping was done using the ocean observing components iteratively co-developed by the [BioEcoOcean project](#). (Fig. 2. Blueprint) Words that did not fit directly within the components included processes like collaboration, cooperation, and interdisciplinary. The audience expressed that the Baltic Sea region is performing well in data collection (34 responses), including monitoring, in-situ and satellite observations and detection of invasive species, among others. Cooperation and coordination also emerged as key strengths in marine life observations in the Baltic Sea.

Figure 2. Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science

The importance of HELCOM in the Baltic Sea region was also acknowledged. Several respondents specifically attributed standard procedures in ocean observation, conservation, and education to HELCOM.

Other aspects of ocean observation in the Baltic that were highlighted as strengths included communication, education, data management, innovation and technology, and interdisciplinarity (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Bar graph on the responses of the audience to 'What they are doing well in the Baltic Sea'.

The sentiments of the audience were echoed by the panel experts, who praised the strong cooperation among institutes and organizations across the Baltic Sea region, as well as the willingness to compromise in support of a shared vision. The panel emphasized the fact that, in consequence, the Baltic Sea region is often held up as an example on how building science into action can be done and how it can make a difference. The role of HELCOM was highlighted as critical to achieving this success.

Question 2: “If you were looking for data on marine life in the Baltic Sea, what was your experience in finding and/or reusing such data? Please put that on a scale from 1 to 6.”

The question aimed to understand the experiences of both the panel and audience in relation to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles, as well as for the other Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), including physical and biogeochemical data. The question sought to assess both the ease of finding data and its reusability.

The responses indicated that it was generally easier for the audience to find physical and biogeochemical data compared to marine life (biology and ecosystem) data in the Baltic Sea. A similar pattern emerged regarding reusability. The audience also noted that in their view and regardless of the EOVS category, finding data was generally easier than reusing it.

Figure 4. Responses of the audience to the ease in finding and reusing data based on the main EOVs.

The panel experts shared their perspective and experiences with respect to the “FAIRness” of oceanographic data in the Baltic Sea. At the regional level, the importance of HELCOM was quoted once more as being essential in promoting FAIR data principles for both environmental and biological data. This includes, for example, the development of adequate data policies and services, such as the HELCOM Map and Data Service (MADS). While reusability of available data remains a challenge, it was noted that scale, purpose, and the question asked are key considerations in the design of sampling. Thus, there are cases where a particular type of data collection for a very specific issue is unavoidable. Good communication and collaboration were identified as critical for unlocking the potential of data, which often remain stored and archived outside of the registered national or EU data repositories. This is particularly true and impactful for locally conducted research and monitoring. A closer cooperation with industry was also noted as important to further unlocking the potential of currently inaccessible or closed data sources.

The panel also discussed optimizing the data use specifically to advance ecosystem modeling and forecasting. On one hand, biological and ecosystem models can leverage the existing value of physical models. On the other hand, it was noted that although the physics and climate modeling community has been successful in using observations to advance modeling, there remain areas to improve around more efficient uptake of new types of measurements such as Argo float and glider data. The use of machine learning techniques, a prominent theme at this conference, was identified as a crucial novel technique to help synthesize and integrate heterogeneous data sources, thereby improving forecasting capacities for both physical and biological applications. In addition to providing more and higher quality open-access data, the panel emphasized the importance of effective communication regarding datasets, including their benefits and limitations. Furthermore, there is a need to better identify measurement priorities and determine the most appropriate methods, considering modelling requirements to optimise data collection.

Question 3: “What is your best advice for collaborating across sectors?”

To enhance understanding and support informed decision-making in the Baltic Sea and other marine environments, cross-sector collaboration is essential. The audience was tasked with providing advice that could improve collaboration across sectors in the Baltic Sea. As with Question 1, the responses were diverse and captured in a word cloud. The most frequently mentioned actions by the audience were ‘Be Open’ and ‘Communication’, followed by “Interdisciplinarity”, “Collaboration”, “FAIR data”, and “Funding”. Some audience members were also of the opinion that informal interactions such as ‘having beer together’ could foster better collaboration across sectors (Fig. 5).

The experts on the panel appreciated the audience’s perspective noting that collaboration in the Baltic Sea region is already strong, but can always be improved. They highlighted the importance of understanding cross-boundary effects, citing offshore wind farm plans and their possible effects on the Baltic Sea as one example of cross-sectorial activities. “Integration” was another key term used in the context of better aligning physical, biogeochemical, and biological data collection and management so that scientists, decision makers, and other users receive adequate information about the “big picture”. The panel also remarked how the typically slow process of developing regional agreements is in fact quite smooth and fast in the Baltic Sea region.

The discussion concluded with a call to raise awareness and foster empathy for the marine environment among the people living off and around the Baltic Sea. Both the panelists and the audience emphasised the importance of broadening and increasing the creativity science communication efforts, not only within institutional frameworks, but also to the individual level.

Finally, the role of marine education was highlighted as vital for fostering long-term change in the way we conduct marine life observations and adopt a holistic approach to science-based decision making.

Figure 5. Word cloud illustrating audience suggestions for enhancing collaboration across sectors in the Baltic Sea.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

1. Strengths in Baltic Sea Ocean Observation

- The audience recognized the Baltic Sea region as performing well in data collection, including in-situ and satellite observations and detection of invasive species.
- Cooperation and coordination were seen as key enablers of successful observation efforts.
- The role of HELCOM was appreciated and also credited with driving standard procedures that support harmonization and consistency in observation.
- Communication, education, data management, innovation and technology, and interdisciplinarity were all viewed as positive contributors to ocean observing efforts in the region.

2. Challenges in Biological and Ecosystem Data

- Compared to physical and biogeochemical data, it was more difficult for the audience to find and reuse marine life (biological/ecosystem) data.
- Data findability was found easier than data reusability, indicating a gap in sharing practices.

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3. Collaboration-Enhancing Practices

- "Be Open" and "Communication" were the most frequently cited strategies to enhance cross-sector collaboration.
- Additional enablers included interdisciplinarity, collaboration, FAIR data principles, and funding.
- Informal spaces (e.g., "having beers together") were suggested as effective for building trust and relationships across sectors.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Greater efforts are needed to improve FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) of marine life data.
- Strengthening informal networks, cross-disciplinary engagement, and sustained ongoing communication will support better collaboration.
- Existing strengths, such as those fostered by HELCOM, can be adapted and applied in other ocean regions.

Role in the Blueprint development

Co-creation is at the centre of BioEcoOcean's approach in creating the Blueprint. The joint identification of the strengths, challenges, and gaps of an established regional collaboration (HELCOM), not only helps in strengthening the Blueprint as a creative problem-solving tool but also provide ways of making Baltic research more globally interoperable and relevant. The inputs from the expert panel and the audience therefore ensures that voices from regional platforms are incorporated in the co-production of the Blueprint therefore amplifying them to shape global solutions.